

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research

Vol. 1, Number 2, September - 2025 | Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN 2764-9733 | ijersearch.org

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17254064

CURRICULUM VITAE AND THE GAP FOR TEACHER TRAINING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to analyze didactics in higher education and the pedagogical approaches presented in the curriculum. It explores the contribution of critical pedagogy to reflecting on the nuances of liberating teaching in a capitalist society. It also explores the importance of supervised teaching and learning as a stimulus for excellent learning. The research was developed through a bibliographic analysis of contemporary authors who discuss Didactics Applied to Higher Education.

Keywords: Curriculum. Didactics. Critical Pedagogy. Supervised Internship. Initial Training.

INTRODUCTION

The objective of this study is to analyze the teaching of didactics in higher education and the preparation of student-teachers to face the challenges of the teaching profession. It aims to understand how the teaching and learning process develops in higher education and the approaches developed by professors to meet the needs of students in the 21st-century knowledge society. It also aims to understand the changing profile of students who are dissatisfied with traditionalist didactics that merely transfer knowledge and do not accept questions. How can we transform the pedagogical curriculum to serve the social actors of this highly questioning knowledge society? The contribution of critical pedagogy, which encourages and supports critical and engaging teaching, provides a teaching-learning process that breaks with the coloniality that persists today.

DEVELOPMENT

Supervised internship and its contribution to initial and continuing education

The initial teacher training process for undergraduate programs addresses numerous issues, ranging from the curriculum to interactions with professors and classmates. Twenty-first-century society is very different from that of the 20th century. Behavioral changes mediated by technology and social media have shaped and are shaping the desire to seek and transmit knowledge. In-person social interactions are being redefined due to COVID-19, which has forced society to confront the importance of in-person interaction over virtual ones. The undergraduate program includes pedagogical practice that aims to strengthen theoretical teaching and learning.

The reconfiguration of challenges related to teacher training drives new research on initial teacher training processes, which implies investigations focused on the development of training actions, exchanges and collective production of knowledge, practical experiences and reflections arising from lived experiences, that is, the processes experienced

within the scope of training. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 2)

The importance of training courses also lies in providing practice in teaching, where theory and practice will be reinterpreted through the reading of the world during teaching.

Indeed, initial teacher training processes play a fundamental role in providing differentiated ways of developing theoretical and practical knowledge, as this inseparability between theory and practice allows the student-teacher to be a participating subject in the professional learning process itself, understanding that training is effective in the professional's interaction with the reality and context of the educational field, a privileged locus for understanding and constructing teaching knowledge and skills. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 4)

Teaching at universities favors initial teacher training which, combined with practice, develops a critical sense for reflective action by providing the means to confront social inequalities resulting from the process of coloniality that still permeate actions in society.

We understand that the relationship between universities and schools needs to be developed as a two-way street, that is, contributions are evidenced in exchanges, because, at the same time that learning materializes in facing problem situations, specific to the school context, enriching the training of the undergraduate, reflective moments are produced that involve school professionals, raised by the critical understanding of the causes and possible solutions to the issues present in pedagogical practice in which the clash with theory is fundamental. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 8)

To become a teacher, it is necessary to have the desire to be one and understand the importance of this profession that contributes to the development and improvement of another human being, be it a child, adolescent, young person or adult. Studying to become a teacher is an exercise in duality. There are times when the exercise will be individual and at others it will be permeated by partnerships. In this sense, the supervised internship is of utmost importance as it provides guidance during professional practice.

Supervised internships, understood as practical work within undergraduate programs, with a

workload, time, and space defined by law, express the mandatory practical experience in teacher training. This category of practice encompasses studies that reflect on the interrelationship between universities and schools, in the practice of learning to be a teacher, mediated by initial training and teaching practice. This provides the student-teacher with challenging experiences, through the unity of theory and practice and the opportunities to better understand the role of the teacher as an agent of change in the social context. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 10)

The need for student-teachers to enter the job market in response to the increasingly scarce workforce in the educational field means that universities prioritize specific knowledge, delegating less attention to teaching disciplines.

Regarding the relationship between universities and schools, studies highlight criticisms of the development of this activity, such as the distance between these institutions, the emphasis on specific disciplines in the area to the detriment of pedagogical disciplines, the dichotomy between theory and practice, the lack of clear guidelines for the development of the internship, the decontextualization of professional training with the world of work, among others. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 10, 11)

We can understand that teacher training is significantly weakened when supervised internship is not conducted assertively.

Thus, the internship becomes a tool for training institutions in the development of practices aimed at training future teaching professionals, so that the undergraduate student learns to be a teacher in the exercise of teaching practice, through teaching experiences that contribute to the construction of professional identity from initial training. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 11)

The importance of supervised internships for students lies in the proportion of their transformation, in their openness to new things, and in creating new possibilities for understanding the world that contribute to the process of decoloniality through teaching activities and theoretical teaching.

In the process of becoming a teacher, the student-intern also develops autonomy, creativity, integration, participation, respect for others, and sensitivity to social and

political issues, dimensions that involve their profession and human emancipation. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 12)

The internship in professional training provides the outline and autonomy for pedagogical practice, which is contemplated with interaction with more experienced colleagues, contributing to the otherness of the social subjects involved.

Practice, when constituted as a teacher training process, can be considered a founding component of initial training, in which the knowledge and skills that support professional development and teaching identity are also developed and generated through practice. (Macêdo and Romanowski, 2025, p. 14)

Didactics in higher education or a gap in the subject offering?

The demands of contemporary times, combined with the demands of capitalism for high professional and technological performance in society, have contributed to the surge in demand for higher education programs. Consequently, the offering of courses at higher education institutions has increased the demand for university professors. To teach at these institutions, faculty are accepted with either a *stricto sensu* or *lato sensu* degree. The *lato sensu* curriculum does not always include the subject of didactics, which ultimately results in learning gaps in teacher training. This gap in academic training does not refer to knowledge itself, but rather to the way in which faculty convey the accumulated knowledge specific to their field.

Add to the discussion the dynamics of modern life, in which higher education students have broad access to information and often need to balance their academic and professional activities, refusing to accept classes that fail to add value. The complaint we see from students is that their professors 'know the subject well, but don't know how to teach it.' That is, they are experts and master the teaching content, yet they fail to use the correct teaching techniques to help them understand. (Santo and Luz, 2013, p. 60)

To clarify the didactics:

Didactics can be defined as a set of activities organized by the teacher aiming to favor the

construction of knowledge by the student, without a normative or even prescriptive character, adjusting to the educational project of a society. (Santo e Luz, 2013 apud FIORE FERRARI; LEYMONIÉ SÁEN, 2007, p. 59)

Therefore, we can conclude that didactics is the way a teacher chooses to convey knowledge to students, using the techniques and approaches they deem most appropriate. Students' criticism of content delivery lies precisely in the didactics chosen by teachers, which do not always meet the needs of students in the knowledge society. This gap results from the fragility of *lato sensu* education, which does not always offer didactics instruction in higher education.

Santo and Luz (2013) claim that didactics is a matter of debate among several scholars and cite José Carlos Libâneo on this topic.

[...] there is no such thing as a student in general, but rather a student living in a society determined, which is part of a specific social group and culture, since these circumstances interfere with your ability to learn [...] A good teacher who aspires to have good teaching skills need to learn every day how to deal with the subjectivity of students, their language, their perceptions, their life practice. Without this disposition, will be unable to pose problems, challenges, questions related to the content, a condition for obtaining a meaningful learning. (LIBÂNEO, 2001, p. 3)

University education sometimes presents itself with a traditionalist approach, with the teacher transmitting knowledge and leaving it to the student to memorize the content for assessments, resulting in a teaching-learning process without interaction, engagement, and critical sense from the students.

About traditional teaching (Santo and Luz, 2013 apud FREIRE, 2007; GIL, 2008 p. 62 and 63)

The practice of teaching in the traditional approach is limited to lectures taught by specialist teachers and the resulting memorization of the content by students. It is the teacher's responsibility to verify whether the content transmitted in the classroom has been rigorously reproduced in the few learning assessment tools available. Although these

traditional concepts do not align with contemporary concepts, unfortunately, we still see them frequently adopted by university professors in their teaching practice, as they tend to reproduce the traditional methods to which they were subjected during their own academic training.

The Portuguese word *aluno* has its origins in the Latin *al-* (negation), *lumnis*, *lumen* (light) and reinforces the ideas of traditional pedagogy of passive and receptive teaching.

The teaching-learning process with a traditionalist approach adopted by university professors is a complex issue. It may be a methodological option and may also be the result of a learning gap in higher education, in the presentation of the pedagogical discipline that is offered in an incipient manner to adequately equip the student-teacher with pedagogical practice.

Critical Pedagogy

In 2021, if he were alive, Paulo Freire would be celebrating his 100th birthday. His work is a reference in numerous studies and a consensus among scholars regarding his contribution to the understanding of life and political emancipation, fostered through education. Freire was concerned with the liberation of consciences, and capitalism was the basis of his critique, believing that this mercantile logic constrains freedom of thought, objectifying social relations.

Popular Education and Youth and Adult Education were the founding foundations of Freire's ideas, gaining visibility, and constituting important references for Critical Pedagogy. His theoretical and practical formulations propose an education for social transformation and the empowerment of individuals mediated by transformative practices and critical consciousness. Thus, Paulo Freire was not a mere spectator of the history of his people. Far from adopting neutral stances, he assumed the position of spokesperson for voices silenced by power dynamics, placing his work and his sociological, historical, and philosophical vision at the service of transforming unequal social structures. (Silva and Campos, 2021, p.

4)

Henry Armand Giroux, closely aligned with Paulo Freire's ideas, focuses on Radical Pedagogy, emphasizing the role of the teacher as an agent of social and political transformation. In the year of Paulo Freire's centenary, Giroux gave an interview to Silva and Campos (2021), where he recounts his friendship and intellectual affinity with Freire on social and political issues.

[...] schools are the primary institutions for educating students for public life [...] that schools must function to provide students with the knowledge, character, and moral vision that build civic courage. (Silva and Campos, 2021 apud (GIROUX, 1999, p. 29) p. 8)

Freire and Giroux advocate for the autonomy of academia to foster critical thinking, a pedagogy centered on liberating consciousnesses to transform them into engaged social actors with the potential for social and political change. Giroux responds to Silva and Campos' (2021) question about curriculum and the role of the teacher:

At the heart of Freire's work is this assumption that teachers are not only central to the pedagogical process but also that they must have control over their working conditions. At the same time, he points to the need for teachers to be critical, informed, willing to take risks, and to challenge the power of those who trade in injustice, produce a paralyzing indifference to social justice, and concentrate power in the hands of a few. (Silva and Campos, 2021, p. 10)

The curriculum is a blueprint for what the course is expected to present and teach students. As such, it is a living instrument that must be constantly revisited and, ideally, not rigidly implemented, preventing changes from occurring, to avoid falling into an authoritarian perspective. The interviewee continues to clarify the curriculum from Freire's perspective.

Freire made clear throughout his work that curriculum is not a predetermined, lifeless catalog of methods. The latter creates dead zones of imagination, disqualifies teachers, and reproduces pedagogies of repression. Paulo's work provides theoretical indicators and a language that offers hope against a debilitating array of pedagogies that largely serve authoritarianism, especially in an era

marked by the rise of right-wing populism and an updated version of fascism. (Silva and Campos, 2021, p. 10)

Giroux and Freire defend the autonomy of educational institutions, the freedom to develop curricula, and the creativity and quality of teaching provided by teachers, with the hope of effectively contributing to the democratic and liberating process provided by engaging teaching and learning.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Initial training with supervised internships provides student teachers with unique opportunities to develop theoretical and practical learning alongside professionals already working in the education field. The exposure to everyday situations and the exchange of experiences enhance the intern's sense of belonging, preparing them for the challenges of a professional career, and underscores the higher education institution's commitment to developing academic excellence with professionals prepared for the demands of the knowledge-based society.

Critical pedagogy highlights the importance of curriculum, with an emphasis on pedagogical discipline, to foster the development of critical professionals who are well-prepared to serve and prepare social actors for the needs of the capitalist world. This study aims to contribute to research in the educational field, focusing on applied didactics for higher education.

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